

**AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF FINANCIAL AND TAX LITERACY AMONG
SALARIED FEMALE EMPLOYEES IN JUNAGADH CITY**

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Abstract:

The research shows that financial and tax literacy among salaried female employees in the Gujarati city of Junagadh. The study's primary goal was to conduct thorough analyses the understanding of financial and focusing on their ability to manage income and making economic decisions and to evaluate a relationship between financial and tax knowledge among salaried female employees. This study investigates that analytical and descriptive research design with the support of primary data collecting using a properly constructed questionnaire with 51 female employee's responses. In this investigation, typical statistical techniques were applied such as chi square test and It's also using Microsoft excel program. The findings of the survey demonstrated that provided female Employees in Junagadh City demonstrate a strong financial self-discipline, as evidenced by a significant majority of respondents maintaining regular saving habits regardless of their income levels. The survey's results showed that promote responsible financial behaviors, enable women to make well informed Making decisions about finances and taxes and improve their economic independence and participation in the formal financial system.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Personal Finance, Tax Literacy, Salaried Female Employees, Junagadh City

1. Introduction

Financial and tax literacy are two significant skills that meaningfully empowerment and socioeconomic development or entities, mostly among salaried female employees. Financial knowledge explains to the skills, understanding and knowledge demanded that make logical and well-informed decision about financials resources. It consists of Investing, managing credit, and budgeting and financial planning. Another, tax literacy consists of the capacity to write, read, interpret, understand written information successfully across in daily life. (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014)⁶

Among women employees obtaining salary on these two types of literacy play a crucial role in meaningful independence, ability to make decisions, and general well-being. Although the raising participation of women in the employment of the workforce, many yet face changes related to limited financial awareness and insufficient understanding of financial policies, documents, digital platforms. (OECD, 2020)⁸ The gap may be a factor in inefficient financial planning, reduced participation Investment prospects and vulnerability to debt. In the digitization of the economy, where financial transactions and information are mostly technology-driven and text-based, the combination of financial and text literacy becomes even more essential. Improving these abilities of women with salaries not only Gender equality. (Remund, 2010)¹⁰

Hence, understanding and perception the level of textual and financial education among salaried female employees needs to be produced effective educational programs, policy interventions, and workplace education programs targeted at empowering women and encouraging inclusive development.

1.1. Relevance of the study

This research is pertinent as it aims to improve the tax and financial literacy of female paid employees in Junagadh. A group that is vital to the formal economy and household income. The study provides information for creating focused awareness campaigns and educational projects by assessing literacy levels, obstacles, and gaps.

1.2. Statement of the problem

Since there is no specific research on the awareness of financial and tax literacy among salaried female in the Junagadh City, I conducted a research paper specifically for salaried women in Junagadh city. In this manner, they are aware how they are aware of both financial and tax literacy, even if they don't know about the other two. In the modern era, awareness of financial and tax literacy plays a vital role for every individual, especially for salaried women to have a perfect and proper management of their money investment saving schemes, as well as the general rules of taxes. such that it influences their financial choices.

2. Literature Review

1) (Priya, K., & Lal, P. 2024) The study was an analysis standard for working individual's financial education women in India. In the study researcher was conducted through a survey about financial topics like Indian women knowledge of saving, investing and insurance. The study main motive was to identify the variable affecting their financial Literacy and how women aware about the knowledge of financial literacy. This study was conducted a data collection gathered a primary data though a survey analysis of 500 working women of different income levels and ages. The study was used a quantitative research design. At the end, the researcher

concluded about the research that a working woman in India was a very little to know about the financial literacy. Accordingly, the researcher also reflects a several factors on women's financial literacy including income, age, education qualification, and about they work experience.

2) (Bhayani, S. J., & Ajmera, B. 2024) In the study shows that, a study the financial inclusion of four districts of Gujarat namely- Rajkot- Bhavnagar-Junagadh and Amreli have been made. The size of the sample is of 200 respondents 50 respondents from all major cities. The researcher, developed a questionnaire to collect primary data. The researcher, classified financial inclusion in four categories- Access of banking services- Financial literacy- usage of financial services-financial inclusion related policy. This investigation found that financial literacy rate is also good among the selected respondents of four cities are prone to access the financial services offered from the banks.

3) (Samal, S. 2022), In the research investigates financial and tax planning of salaried employees. In the research, the researcher main objective was to decide the pattern of savings and salaried employees, to investigate the teaching women's financial knowledge gap and socioeconomic background. The primary data utilized in the research was acquired properly through respondents. A standardized questionnaire was used to collect data from the Saga's female teaching faculty. The research was used in Descriptive research. As stated in the study, female teaching faculty members have. middling aware of financial decisions and are not well-versed in topics like credit cards and compound interest, but they do choose trustworthy putting choices including bank deposits and insurance.

4) (Mahra, A. K. 2016) In the study researcher was conducted an empirical assessment of financial literacy and pattern of savings, investment behavior of woman teaching faculties in Sagar region. The main observation by research in this research was, to evaluate and understand the savings and investment patterns of the women teaching faculties. The researcher collected gathered information from main data via a questionnaire with 332 sample responded. They used percentage analysis statical tools. The Research suggested that, women will aware for financial and budgeting plans for a future. the research conducted the conclusion was the woman teaching faculties needed to aware a financial literacy as well they understood female investors select financial organization familiarity.

5) (Bhushan, P. & Medury, Y. 2013) The goal of this study, Determining Tax Literacy of Salaried Individuals, An Empirical Analysis. The study examines in a few Himachal Pradesh districts using an analytical and descriptive study approach, and based on primary data collected through the use of a structured survey from 516 respondents sample size. multistage sampling was employee, including factors including, income, education qualification, age, gender, kind of employment, and place of employment. ANOVA and

percentage analysis were used as statistical methods. The study conclude tax literacy is poor and that, with the exception of geographic region, demographic and socioeconomic characteristics have a substantial impact.

3. Objective of the study

- 1) To analyze & identify gap the level of financial & tax literacy among salaried female employees.
- 2) To study the relationship between saving habits of respondent & income level of female employees.
- 3) To suggest the measure for enhancing financial and tax literacy.

4. Significance of the study

Making wise financial decisions and avoiding any financial dangers may be facilitated by Possessing a solid comprehension of financial literacy. The Junagadh City, which encompasses both rural and urban regions, has seen a rise in the quantity of women working for pay in recent years. Consequently, even if they are unaware of financial and tax literacy, they are conscious of how it affects their finances decisions.

5. Scope of the study

The study's scope is confined to salaried female in Junagadh City. The conclusions are founded on a limited sample and are applicable within the defined geographical area.

6. Research Gap

The study title, " An analytical Study of Financial and Tax Literacy Among Salaried Female Employees in Junagadh City," indicates that while a number of researchers have examined financial and tax literacy in India, that focuses on area-specific studies, particularly with regard to salary-based women in the Junagadh City. Research on salaried women's knowledge and comprehension of tax laws, money management, tax plan savings, and online tax return submission is also lacking. There hasn't been much research done on the connections between financial and tax literacy in addition to the relationships between elements such as marital status, income, and education.

7. Research Methodology

7.1 Research Design

The research study is based on both descriptive and analytical.

7.2 Sources of Data

The study uses a structured questionnaire to collect primary data. administered to salaried female employees.

7.3 Population of the Study

The population of the Research comprises salaried female employees working in various sectors including education, banking, healthcare, government departments, and private organisations within Junagadh City.

7.4 Sample Size

A sample of 51 salaried female employees has been selected for the purpose of the study.

7.5 Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling has been employed to select respondents, considering accessibility and practical constraints.

7.6 Data Collection Instrument

A structured questionnaire has been used as the primary data collection instrument.

7.7 Tools and Techniques of Analysis

The Chi-Square test was used to investigate the relationship between the taxation knowledge and financial awareness of salaried female employees.

8. Data Analysis and Interpretation

- **Hypothesis of the Study:**

H₀ = There is no significant difference between Monthly Income and the habit of saving a portion of income among respondents.

H₁ = There is significant difference between Monthly Income and the habit of saving a portion of income among respondents.

Table No 1: Showing Observed Frequency by Chi-square test

Monthly Income	Save a Portion of Income			Grand Total
	No	Sometimes	Yes, always	
Above Rs. 60,000		1	5	6
Rs. 10,000 to Rs.20,000	1	3	9	13
Rs. 20,000 to Rs. 40,000	2	8	14	24
Rs. 40,000 to Rs. 60,000		2	6	8
Grand Total	3	14	34	51

(Source – Primary Data Collected Through Questionnaire Survey)

• **Interpretation:**

Table No. 1 shows the relationship between respondents' monthly income and their habit of saving a portion of income. It is clearly observed that saving behavior is strong among the respondents irrespective of their income level. Out of 51 respondents, a significant majority 34 reported that they always save a portion of their income, 14 save sometimes, and only 3 do not save at all, indicating a high level of financial awareness and disciplined financial planning. The largest group belongs to the Rs. 20,000 to Rs. 40,000 income categories, where most respondents consistently practice saving, and similar positive saving patterns are evident in both lower and higher income groups. Overall, the data reflects a strong and consistent saving habit across different income levels, suggesting responsible financial.

Table No 2: Showing Expected Frequency by Chi-square test

Monthly Income	Save a Portion of Income			Grand Total
	No	Sometimes	Yes, always	
Above Rs. 60,000	0.35	1.65	4.00	6
Rs. 10,000 to Rs.20,000	0.76	3.57	8.67	13
Rs. 20,000 to Rs. 40,000	1.41	6.59	16.00	24
Rs. 40,000 to Rs. 60,000	0.47	2.20	5.33	8
Grand Total	3	14	34	51

(Source – Primary Data Collected Through Questionnaire Survey)

• **Interpretation:**

Table No. 2 Shows the expected frequencies of people's saving behavior across different monthly income groups. It suggests that most individuals are likely to save regularly, while very few do not save at all and some save occasionally. Higher income groups tend to have more people expected to save consistently, whereas lower income groups show a slightly higher chance of occasional saving. The largest group belongs

to the Rs. 20,000 to Rs. 40,000 income categories, where most respondents consistently practice saving, and similar positive saving patterns are evident in both lower and higher income groups.

Table No 3: Finding of the Chi-square test

P value = 0.954112	
P value < 0.05	H ₀ Rejected
P value > 0.05	H ₀ Accepted
0.954112 > 0.05	
H₀ Accepted	

- Table No. 3 finding that salaried female employees in Junagadh City. majority of respondents maintaining regular saving habits regardless of their income levels. A null hypothesis (H₀) was accepted.
- The research study used standard statistical analysis using the Chi-square test, that indicates, there is not a significant association between monthly income and saving habit.
- Awareness about tax & financial knowledge, along with Many respondents depend on others like., advisors, family. So that there is a need to improve it.
- Out of the 51 respondents, over half (25 participants, 49%) said they successfully manage their assets in combination with paying income tax statements.

9. Suggestion of the Study:

Government and educational institutional Should be conducted the Standardized and knowledgeable programs & Proper guidance for Improve awareness about the financial and tax knowledge among salaried female employees in Junagadh city.

10. Limitations of the Study

- The research is founded on small sample size of 51 respondents.
- The findings cannot be generalised to populations or other regions.
- The study is collected data from a questionnaire, that the results depend upon the responses given by the participants.

Conclusion

The Present study shows that the financial and tax literacy are play a vital role in salaried female employees in Junagadh city. The study also reveals those demographic factors like, income level, education qualification, gender, age etc. The Chi-square test, finds that there is no significant association within a monthly income level and saving practices. The study will suggest that Government and educational institutional Should be conducted the Standardized and knowledgeable programs. Therefore, the study concluded that, need to conducting knowledgeable workshops, Awareness programmes, to raise the standard of financial and tax literacy, that will not only assist in personal development while simultaneously making a contribution and improvement to the economic development of our society.

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